

Growth and production of cruciferous vegetables (*brassicaceae*) in subsoil land with different level of cow manure

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ABSTRACT

Subsoils have generally low fertility compared to common soil, although they were prepared to be used for planting for years. This research aimed to determine different dosage of cow manure on growth and production of seasonal cruciferous crops (*brassicaceae*) in subsoil. This research was conducted in April – May 2018, located at Experimental Field in Faculty of Animal and Agricultural Sciences, Diponegoro University, Semarang City, Central Java. This research used split block design. The main plot was three common variety of cruciferous vegetables (V1 = Pakchoy, V2 = Kailan, V3 = Choysum), The subplot was dosage of cow manure consisted in four levels (P1 = 0 ton/ha, P2 = 10 ton/ha, P3 = 20 ton/ha, P4 = 30 ton/ha). The observed parameters were shoot and root production, dry substances, harvest index and nitrogen uptake. Those data were statistically analyzed using ANOVA and followed by Fisher's Least Significant Different (LSD). There was an interaction between variety of crops and cow manure's dose in root production and nitrogen uptake. Choysum was the best variety planted in subsoil condition. Choysum had the most value of shoot production, root production, and nitrogen uptake, and significantly better than others. Pakchoy has the best harvest index ratio, while Kailan has the best dry substances. Cow manure at 30 ton/ha was the best treatment for increasing shoot and root production.

Keywords: choysum, cow manure, Kailan, Pakchoy, subsoil

INTRODUCTION

Subsoil is generally reversed from the initial arrangement where the topsoil is located under the subsoil (Mawazi and Susilo 2016). Those materials are stacked on the top of productive soils, which can inhibit plant growth and reduce soil productivity (Margareththa 2010). To improve soil fertility, revitalization of land is needed by adding organic materials such as organic

fertilizer. Land revitalization can be maximized for agricultural production with land improvement so that land is more productive and not neglected.

The application of manure or organic fertilizer can improve soil structure, soil microbiological activity, and increasing nutrient sources for plants (Lingga and Marsono 2013). Manure has a long-term effect that can improve soil structure and soil aeration (Suwahyono 2017).

One of the horticultural commodities that can be used on less-fertile land and able to grown adaptively on Ultisols is the cruciferous plants or mustards (Adriani and Syahfari 2017). Mustard is a group of plants from the *Brassica* family which production came from the leaves or flowers as vegetables, both fresh and processed. Mustard includes several species of *Brassicaceae* which are sometimes similar to each other.

Choysum is a type of leaf vegetable plant and belongs to seasonal crops (short-lived). Kailan also have known as Chinese Broccoli, while Pakchoy is known as Chinese Cabbage. Both of these vegetables look similar to mustard greens (Choysum, toसान). Kailan's taste is more bitter than Pakchoy. Kailan texture is more like asparagus, while Pakchoy is closer to green mustard. Cruciferous plants can grow in the lowlands (5-1200 m asl) to high, but has grown optimally in the highlands with cool air (Haryanto et al. 2007).

Cruciferous plants are suitable to grow and adapt to almost all types of soil, both on mineral soils that are light-textured to heavy-textured even on peat soils (Setiawati et al. 2007). Soil acidity (pH) for optimal plant growth is 5.5-6.5 and optimal temperature of 20-25°C with rainfall more than 200 mm/month with suitable air humidity between 80-90%.

Badan Pusat Statistika (BPS) have mentioned that cruciferous vegetables or *Brassicaceae* has a good prospects based on the production in 2011-2015. In 2006, production of cruciferous vegetables has been decreased from average production of 25,370 from 28,730 ton/ha in 2005. Cruciferous vegetables production might be increased by adding some organic ingredients like cow manure (Barokah et al. 2017)

This study aims to determine the effect of cow manure dosage on the growth and quality of Cruciferous vegetables (*Brassicaceae*) on subsoil, and to provide information about cruciferous vegetables that able to planted in subsoil which has been enriched by cow manure.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was conducted in February - May 2018, located in the AgroTechnoPark and Laboratory of Plant Ecology and Production, Faculty of Animal and Agricultural Sciences, Diponegoro University, Semarang. Materials that prepared were Choysum (var. *Shinta*), Kailan (var. *Full White*), and Pakchoy

(var. Takii) seeds, cow manure, pesticides from cow urine, shovels, seedling wooden boxes, sprayers, UV-VIS spectrophotometer, flame photometer, oven, furnace and stationary analytical scales. The location has a climate characteristic with maximum air temperature of 35°C and minimum air temperature of 24°C.

Research were conducted in several stages, there were research preparation and research implementation. Research preparation includes the subsoil identification through physical identification (textures and soil colour) and chemical identification (content of N, P, K and C-organic). Land that has been identified mechanically was prepared to the group of beds.

The implementation of the research included nurseries, adding treatments of cow manure, planting, maintenance and harvesting. Nurseries were done by choosing the good quality of seeds. Soil mixed with cow manure prepared for the planting medium, which inserted into the seedlings wooden boxes. Treatments were given by adding cow manure based on the dosages that were planned and will be given after tillage. Planting were done when the seedlings has been reach 17 DAS (days after sowing). Maintenance have include watering, re-planting and pests controlling. Harvesting is done in 45 DAP (days after planting) by pulling out the whole plant.

This research used split block design with three replications. The main plot was three common variety of cruciferous vegetables (V1 = Pakchoy, V2 = Kailan, V3 = Choysum), the subplot was dosage of cow manure consisted in four levels (P1 = 0 ton/ha, P2 = 10 ton/ha, P3 = 20 ton/ha, P4 = 30 ton/ha). Total experimental unit was 36 plots. The observed parameters were shoot and root production, dry substances, harvest index and nitrogen uptake. Those data were statistically analyzed using ANOVA and followed by Fisher's Least Significant Different (LSD) at 5% level.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Shoot production

The results of the variance analysis showed that there was no interaction between the variety of crops and the dose of cow manure against the shoot production. The average shoot production in each treatment is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Shoot Production Average in Different Varieties of *Brassicaceae* and Dosages of Cow Manure.

Dosage of Cow Manure (tonha ⁻¹)	Variety of Crops			Average
	Pakchoy (V1)	Kailan (V2)	Choysum (V3)	
	----- (gplot ⁻¹) -----			
0 tonha ⁻¹ (P0)	2087.20	326.00	3300.00	1904.40 ^a
10 ton ha ⁻¹ (P1)	3192.00	936.00	4432.00	2853.33 ^{ab}
20 ton ha ⁻¹ (P2)	3664.00	553.60	7574.00	3930.53 ^b
30 ton ha ⁻¹ (P3)	4804.40	1130.80	7358.00	4431.07 ^b
Average	3436.90 ^b	736.60 ^a	5666.00 ^c	

Description: Different superscripts showed differences significantly based on Fishers LSD at 5% level of confidence. Each plot area = 1.62 m²

Choysum have the bigger results in shoot production compared with both of Pakchoy and Kailan in dose of 0 – 30 ton/ha cow manure. Dose of 30 ton/ha cow manure provided the highest average of shoot production, and significantly different with 0, 10, 20 ton/ha respectively. Cow manure supplies essential nutrients such as N, P, and K as materials that lead an important role to the growth of cruciferous vegetables. Sompotan (2013) mentioned that the higher dosage of organic compounds contained higher concentration level of N, P, and K than other that was absorbed for metabolic process. Organic compounds affect the water holding capacity which improved roots penetration easily to absorb nutrients. Photosynthesis rate lead a role to impact shoot production which increase the number leaves. The increasing number of leaves will provide the higher production of cruciferous vegetables. Illa et al. (2017) said that shoot production is also associated with the number of leaves and leaf area, as the results of their physiological growth.

Root production

The results of the variance analysis showed that there was an interaction between the variety of crops and the dose of cow manure against the root production. The average root production in each treatment is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Root Production Average in Different Varieties of *Brassicaceae* and Dosages of Cow Manure.

Dosage of Cow Manure (tonha ⁻¹)	Variety of Crops			Average
	Pakchoy (V1)	Kailan (V2)	Choysum (V3)	
	----- (g plot ⁻¹) -----			
0 tonha ⁻¹ (P0)	256.80 ^a	146.00 ^a	232.00 ^a	211.60
10 ton ha ⁻¹ (P1)	246.00 ^a	178.00 ^{ab}	356.00 ^b	260.00
20 ton ha ⁻¹ (P2)	240.00 ^a	162.40 ^{ab}	488.00 ^b	296.80
30 ton ha ⁻¹ (P3)	415.60 ^b	223.20 ^b	462.00 ^b	366.93
Average	289.60	177.40	384.50	

Description: Different superscripts showed differences significantly based on Fishers LSD at 5% level of confidence. Each plot area = 1.62 m²

Choysum has the bigger results in root production compared with both of Pakchoy and Kailanin in dose of 0 – 30 ton/ha cow manure. Dose of 30 ton/ha cow manure provided the highest average of root production, and significantly different with 0, 10, 20 ton/ha respectively. Cow manure influences cruciferous vegetables. The application of cow manure has an effect on the wet weight and dry weight of the crops, as the result of accumulation of photosynthate in the form of plant biomass and water content in the leaves. Water content is the main factor that determining wet weight. Cow manure would improve the soil physical properties that is less-fertile soil including water, chemical and biological content. Sustainable application of cow manure will increase land productivity, thus helping roots to penetrate deeper into the soil and have the ability to absorb optimally nutrients and water. Mukti et al. (2017) stated that application of cow manure can increase nutrient content, especially organic carbon, to increase the process of nutrient absorption to a maximum limit. Suwahyono (2017) added that cow manure has a long period effect to improve soil structure and soil aeration.

Dry Substances

The results of the variance analysis showed that there was no interaction between the variety of crops and the dose of cow manure against the dry substances. The average of dry substances in each treatment is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Dry Substances Average in Different Varieties of *Brassicaceae* and Dosages of Cow Manure.

Dosage of Cow Manure (tonha ⁻¹)	Variety of Crops			Average
	Pakchoy (V1)	Kailan (V2)	Choysum (V3)	
	------(%)-----			
0 tonha ⁻¹ (P0)	8.66	15.51	6.40	10.19 ^b
10 ton ha ⁻¹ (P1)	7.91	13.95	5.17	9.01 ^{ab}
20 ton ha ⁻¹ (P2)	8.81	14.15	4.71	9.22 ^b
30 ton ha ⁻¹ (P3)	6.32	14.16	4.52	8.33 ^a
Average	7.93 ^b	14.44 ^c	5.20 ^a	

Description: Different superscripts showed differences significantly based on Fishers LSD at 5% level of confidence. Each plot area = 1.62 m²

Kailan has the most results in dry substances compared with both of Pakchoy and Choysum in dose of 0 – 30 ton/ha cow manure. Kailan has the most thickness leaves compared with others, because it has a similarity with Kale’s and Broccoli’s leaves, while the two others looks more like Cabbage. Control treatment of cow manure (0 ton/ha) has the bigger results of dry substances, but not significant with 20 ton/ha. Dry substances is possibly influenced by the amount of photosynthate that has been stored in plant tissues, including N and P as the major factors in vegetative growth. Dry substances reflect organic matter produced from photosynthetic activity. Nitrogen is absorbed by plants in the form of nitrate or ammonium, depending on the type of soil conditions and soil aeration. Mukti et al. (2017) said that the average nitrogen content in plant tissues is 2-4% dry content/substances.

Harvest Index

The results of the variance analysis showed that there was no interaction between the variety of crops and the dose of cow manure against the harvest index. The average harvest index in each treatment is presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Harvest Index Average in Different Varieties of *Brassicaceae* and Dosages of Cow Manure.

Dosage of Cow Manure (tonha ⁻¹)	Variety of Crops			Average
	Pakchoy (V1)	Kailan (V2)	Choysum (V3)	
	------(%)-----			
0 tonha ⁻¹ (P0)	72.48	43.54	67.51	61.18
10 ton ha ⁻¹ (P1)	77.82	44.30	68.05	63.39
20 ton ha ⁻¹ (P2)	79.14	44.77	63.92	62.61
30 ton ha ⁻¹ (P3)	74.57	47.88	62.73	61.73
Average	76.00 ^c	45.12 ^a	65.55 ^b	

Description: Different superscripts showed differences significantly based on Fishers LSD at 5% level of confidence. Each plot area = 1.62 m²

The application of cow manure did not significantly affect harvest index of Pakchoy, Kailan and Choysum, but the best results of harvest index obtained from 10 ton/ha. The harvest index of Pakchoy (76%) is significantly bigger than the others (Kailan and Choysum). Harvest index is an information of crop yields which calculate the quantity of harvest that determine the bigger yield higher. Those all varieties did not show any interaction with cow manure. This might being caused by nutrient contents of soil which is decreasing, caused by environmental factor si.e. rainfall. Rainfall causes nutrients leaching from the subsoil which crops unable to absorb and lead to less productivity of harvest. Haryadi et al. (2015) stated that nutrient contents of soil directly affect the growth and production of crops, as the result of it, crops will be grown and produce optimally.

Nitrogen Uptake

The results of the variance analysis showed that there was an interaction between the variety of crops and the dose of cow manure against the nitrogen uptake. The average nitrogen uptake in each treatment is presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Nitrogen Uptake Average in Different Varieties of *Brassicaceae* and Dosages of Cow Manure.

Dosage of Cow Manure (tonha ⁻¹)	Variety of Crops			Average
	Pakchoy (V1)	Kailan (V2)	Choysum (V3)	
	----- (g plot ⁻¹) -----			
0 tonha ⁻¹ (P0)	2.642 ^a	1.478 ^a	2.367 ^a	2.162
10 ton ha ⁻¹ (P1)	3.195 ^a	5.625 ^a	2.487 ^a	3.769
20 ton ha ⁻¹ (P2)	3.959 ^a	1.047 ^a	4.281 ^b	3.096
30 ton ha ⁻¹ (P3)	3.839 ^a	2.553 ^a	4.104 ^b	3.499
Average	3.409	2.676	3.310	

Description: Different superscripts showed differences significantly based on Fishers LSD at 5% level of confidence. Each plot area = 1.62 m²

Nitrogen uptake of Choysum was significantly better than Kailan and Pakchoyin in dose of 0 – 10 ton/ha cow manure, but not significant at 20 ton/ha cow manure. The higher N uptake capacity of crops will be more better growth and its production. Prsetya et al. (2009) stated that high nitrogen uptake in crops can affect crops growth and production. Nitrogen availability is needed for the chlorophyll synthesis, which will affect photosynthetic/assimilation rate. Carbohydrates are the basic ingredients for building plant morphology which influence the formation of leaf. Hamim (2004) mentioned that photosynthesis activity will produce more photosynthate, it will affect the dry weight of the shoots, increase the production of photosynthate.

CONCLUSIONS

Choysum was the best variety that give better growth in subsoil reserved. Choysum had the most value of shoot production, root production, and nitrogen uptake, and significantly better than two others. Pakchoy had the best harvest index ratio, while Kailan had the best dry substances. Dose of 30 ton/ha of cow manure was the best treatment for increasing shoot and root production, while 10 ton/ha of cow manure was the best treatment for harvest index and nitrogen uptake.

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